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The power of music in education

Annotation: The present article highlights the importance of music in education and its impact on pupils.

Key words: cognitive skills, academic performance, stress, language, endorphin, dopamine, serotonin, education, students, emotional well-being.

Music has been highly appreciated since past times as it may either lift a person's mood or get it down depending on the genre of the music. Have you ever thought what kind of benefits music can bring to students if it is implemented in schools? Would it have positive outcomes in general? You will find some possible answers to your questions in the following paragraphs.

Music has the power to enhance cognitive skills and emotional well-being. Research has shown that engaging in music during school times can positively impact on overall academic performance of pupils. The main reason is because music has the ability to heal and calm down people taking unnecessary thoughts out of the mind which accordingly reflects on pupils' academic success. It influences on various areas of development be it learning languages, mathematics and vocabulary.

You may have been thinking how music can help to learn languages. The person who listens to music has a tendency to understand music pitch, rhythm and tone better which are the most important elements of a language. As those kinds of people feel the music they are highly focused on what they are doing which helps them to learn faster and master one language proficiently.

Apart from that, in hotels you may have heard classical songs that play on the background. This also creates a very different atmosphere helping most of the people to relax and do their job with enjoyment and focus. It may be used during breaks in a workplace to help gain more energy and come back to temporarily suspended activity. Music is also used while pupils are debating as a group to help them to be faster and creative as music is one of the primary "motor" that generates new creative ideas. Consequently, music in education has a very positive impact on academic success of most students.

Music in education has been researched that it releases stress level, depression and anxiety. If you don't think so, try to listen to a piece of music or play any musical instrument after which you won't notice how it triggered the release of endorphin, dopamine and serotonin being neurotransmitters that have an association with getting pleasure and joy. If you come back to your task after doing that kind of "musical" procedure it would be much more effective and efficient.

In conclusion, music in education can give positive results in academic achievements of pupils as they won't only be busy with doing mundane outdated exercises but can have much fun substituting with musical performances.

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